

Mathematical simulation of the results of temperature measurements at the machining of the polymeric composites materials

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Abstract: - Composite materials with polymeric matrix randomly reinforced with glass fibres are used in industry due to their superior characteristics, in comparison with classic materials. Although composite products can be obtained in final shape as a result of manufacturing process, using specific manufacturing technologies, sometimes these have to be machined by milling work. The determination of possible errors occurring at the measurement of the temperature from the cutting area during milling process, with a virtual instrument made in graphical programming environment - LabVIEW and mathematical simulation of the results obtained which contribute significantly to the correct estimation of the temperatures values from the cutting area. Knowing these estimated values, the optimal parameters of cutting process can determine parameters which will ensure the quality of products, imposed by their functional role.

Key-Words: - polymeric composites, milling work, temperature, errors, LabVIEW, mathematical simulation.

1 Introduction

The products made from composite materials with polymeric matrix, reinforced random with fiberglass are generally obtained in the final shape, as a result of moulding process, using fabrication technology that are called „near net shape” (Resin Transfer Moulding, Pressure Moulding, Hand Moulding) [1].

Due to the technical conditions imposed by the functional role of these products, their peripheral surfaces can't be obtained in conformity with the dimensional and quality imposed requirements, using specific manufacturing process, are mechanically machined, especially by milling work. The milling process of the products made by composites materials with polymeric matrix, is also used, not only to eliminate the manufacturing defects of parts obtained by moulding process (mould marks), but also for sampling the test specimen from products made from composite materials with polymeric matrix, for different types of tests.

In figure 1 there are displayed products from composite materials with polymeric matrix reinforced random with fiber glass, obtained by spray moulding and in figure 2 there are the same products after their milling work.

The products were made by SC ROMTURINGIA SRL from Câmpulung Muscel [1].

Fig.1. Product obtained by spray moulding

Fig. 2. Product machined by milling

The milling work of the composite materials with polymeric matrix randomly reinforced with fiber glass is associated with the specific events of the processing of these materials that restrict the cutting process [2]. Thermal phenomena, that inevitably accompany the cutting process of these materials, have a significant influence on the material and a less influence of the cutting tool and, on the cutting formation process as well. The gradual temperature increase in the contact area between the cutting tool and the working surface can cause chemical reactions, with structural transformation of the matrix composite, which can lead to the damage of the cut surface and to the wear of the cutting tool [1]. Different thermal coefficients of matrix and reinforcement materials can also lead to breaking the interface between fiber and matrix. Low resistance to high temperature of the composite material is attributed to the low resistance of the matrix material. The high values of the temperature have as affect melting of matrix and, even molecular decomposition of its. This phenomenon is also determined by low thermal conductivity of the polymeric materials. The high values of temperature in the cutting zone can develop internal tensions between fiber and matrix, due to the different expansion coefficients of the constituent elements and it can also modify the matrix properties and, change the composite material properties, included.

Based on the above mentioned statements, it is necessary to control the maximum temperature developed during the milling process of the composite materials with polyester resin matrix.

The cutting parameters that will be adopted have to ensure lower temperatures rather than thermal degradation temperature of the matrix material, in the contact area between piece and cutting tool, during the cutting process.

2 Statistics processing of the experimental data

For the experimental study there were used composites materials with polyester resin matrix AROPOL S 599, reinforced random with EC 12-2400 fiberglass type, containing 30% glass fibers. The samples were made at S.C. ROMTURINGIA S.R.L., a certificated company in composites manufacturing, and they were plates of 200×200×10 (mm).

Literature recommends using special cutting tools for the processing of polymeric composites reinforced with glass fibers that are made from tungsten carbide with cobalt binder.

2.1 The method and equipment used

To study the thermal condition, to the milling of composite materials with polymeric matrix reinforced with fiberglass infrared thermography method was used. This method consists in detecting, from distance, the infrared radiation emitted by the product that is under consideration and transforming the information obtained by scanning surface point by point into a visible image which can show the temperature in any point.

The method and equipment used permit the examination of inaccessible areas without direct contact with the products analyzed, but provided that there should be open space between the analyzer and researched area.

To study the thermal conditions from the cutting area there was used an infrared ThermoCAM- SC 640 camera, which allows the acquisition and storage of data during processing. This feature is very useful for processing by milling the material studied, because there are significant temperature variations from one area to another of the material. The milling work was performed on a universal milling machine FSU 22 (figure 3).

Fig. 3. Experimental stand for the study of the temperature

Data analysis was performed using specialized software, ThermoCAM Resresearcher Professional 2.8 SR-2, which allows providing the temperature at any point on the thermogram, showing minimum, mean and maximum temperature (figure 4), the chart of temperature variation (figure 5), so on.

Fig. 4. Minimum, mean and maximum temperature values from cutting area

Fig. 5. Temperature variation at the cylindrical-frontal milling

It was experimentally found that has not achieved the same maximum temperature values at the temperature measurements repeated under the same experimental conditions. These results were affected by three types of errors: gross errors, systematic errors and random errors. Therefore there were done 15 experimental tests to analyze the influence of the factors that generate errors on the measurement results and, implicitly, on the variables that want to be determined.

To determine the maximum temperature in the cutting zone, cutting regime parameters adopted in the cylindrical-frontal milling were as follows:

- cutting speed, $v = 37,69$ m/min;
- cutting feed speed, $v_f = 160$ mm/min;
- axial cutting depth, $a_a = 2$ mm;
- radial cutting depth, $a_r = 6$ mm.

2.2. The elimination of the data affected by gross errors

For the temperature measurement released into the cutting zone, we have taken into account the identification and analysis of the influence of the main factors that produce gross errors. During the experimental researches it has been found that, the resulted chips at the milling of these materials, significantly contribute to the increasing temperature in cutting area. The chips, that are heat carrier, produce the clogging of the cutting tool. This fact contributes to increasing the temperature in the cutting tool and, as well as, to the increase of temperature into cutting zone. A dust outlet special device was added at the experimental stand to evacuate the chips from cutting area that were resulted during milling process of the composite materials. Another factor which contributes to the appearance of the gross errors is the human operator. A working procedure was drawn up to prevent appearance of the gross errors due to the human operator. He has to respect this measurement methodology.

For experimental tests, the maximum values of achieved temperature were recorded and saved into a text file. The saved data were processed with a virtual instrument made in graphical programming environment - LabVIEW. The virtual instrument can detect the experimental values that are affected by gross errors. These errors are almost present in any measurement process.

When the program is run, the values affected by gross errors are identified and then are eliminated for calculus (figure 6). A measured value x_i is affected by gross errors if the condition imposed by Chauvenet criteria (1) is verified [3].

$$|x_i - \bar{x}| > \sigma \times z \quad (1)$$

where:

\bar{x} - is the media of the measured values (2);

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n} \quad (2)$$

σ - standard deviation of experimental values

(3);

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}} \quad (3)$$

n - number of experiments;

$$z = \frac{0,435 - 0,862 \times a}{1 - 3,604 \times a + 3,213 \times a^2} \quad (4)$$

where:

$$a = \frac{2 \times n - 1}{4 \times n} \quad (5)$$

This calculus, which is according to the above mentioned mathematical relations, was made with a virtual instrument developed in graphical programming environment – LabVIEW [4]. Figure 6 presents Front Panel of the virtual instrument and

figure 7 shows the Block Diagram. In the Front Panel there are implemented Controls and Indicators and that is user interface. In the block diagram there was added the code using Vis and structures to control the front panel objects.

Fig. 6. Front Panel

Fig. 7. Block Diagram

When the virtual instrument runs [4], if maximum or minimum values affected by gross error exist, according to condition 1, these values are eliminated from sample and the calculus is remade for the values that have remained.

The application can be used unconcerned by the number of experimental tests of the studied sample. This is automatically determined by the program. The application allows either direct input into the control panel through the element named "Measured Values" or it can read directly the data by the ThermoCAM Resharcner Professional 2.8 SR-2 software from the text file saved to personal computer (figure 8), selecting input method in the program with control element called "Select the input method".

Fig. 8. Text file with measured values

When we select the option "Read data from file", the control element used for the introduction of measured values in the application, it becomes invisible.

2.3. Check the randomness

Proposed application allows verification of randomness of the sample with experimental values, using the algorithm described below (Young test).

$$\delta^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \times \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (x_{i+1} - x_i)^2 \quad (6)$$

$$M = \frac{\delta^2}{\sigma^2} \quad (7)$$

It is determine *M* with the relationship 7 and the value obtained is compared with lower critical value

VCI and *VCS* upper critical value (8). These values are determined with relations 9 and 10.

$$VCI < M < VCS \quad (8)$$

$$VCI = 0,491 + 0,081 \times n - 0,003 \times n^2 \quad (9)$$

$$VCS = 3,317 - 1,057 \times e^{-8,919 \times n^{-0,941}} \quad (10)$$

When the application ran, the randomness of the sample experimental obtained values was revealed and the condition 8 is satisfied. The influence of systematic errors on the experimental results was significantly reduced by monitoring external factors measurement system, such as temperature and humidity, the values of these parameters were kept constant during milling process.

3. Mathematical modeling of the experimental results

To study the thermal cutting area, taken independent variables considered are: cutting speed *v* [m / min], cutting feed speed *v_f* [mm / min] *a_a* axial cutting depth [mm] and radial cutting depth *a_r* [mm]. Depending on the number of variables, the type for the mathematical model proposed to be determined is:

$$\theta = f(v, v_f, a_a, a_r), \hat{m} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}; \quad (11)$$

$$\theta = A_0 \times v^{a_1} \times v_f^{a_2} \times a_a^{a_3} \times a_r^{a_4} \quad (12)$$

where:

θ is temperature

A₀ – the coefficient of the polytrophic relation,

$$A_0 = e^{a_0} = 2,718281^{a_0} \quad (13)$$

a₀, *a₁*, *a₂*, *a₃*, and *a₄* - polytrophic exponents corresponding to the parameters considered.

For the three levels of variation of the process parameters (-1, 0, +1), natural independent variables coded were established based on the data recommended by literature and the possibilities of the milling machine.

Experimental results obtained from milling cylinder-front are presented in Table 2. Processing of experimental results was performed using the program to determine the multivariable regression functions REGS. Regression function obtained from cylinder-front milling is:

$$\theta = 40,6059 \times v^{0,068} \times v_f^{0,067} \times a_a^{0,154} \times a_r^{0,152} \quad (14)$$

Tabelul 2. Experimental results

Temperature θ [$^{\circ}$ C]								
Working material: <i>composite with polymeric matrix AROPOL S 599 random reinforced with fiber glass EC 12-2400</i>								
The factorial program P2.1				v [m/min]	v_f [mm/min]	a_a [mm]	a_r [mm]	θ [$^{\circ}$ C]
-1	-1	-1	-1	18,84	100	1	3	79,6
+1	-1	-1	+1	75,39	100	1	12	107,5
-1	+1	-1	+1	18,84	250	1	12	104
+1	+1	-1	-1	75,39	250	1	3	94,5
-1	-1	+1	+1	18,84	100	4	12	123,5
+1	-1	+1	-1	75,39	100	4	3	107,8
-1	+1	+1	-1	18,84	250	4	3	104,4
+1	+1	+1	+1	75,39	250	4	12	142,1
0	0	0	0	37,69	160	2	6	106,3
0	0	0	0	37,69	160	2	6	107,8
0	0	0	0	37,69	160	2	6	106
0	0	0	0	37,69	160	2	6	107,1

Functions type $\theta = e^{a_0} \times v^{a_1} \times v_f^{a_2} \times a_a^{a_3} \times a_r^{a_4}$

Based on the obtained results at the milling of composite materials, a suggestive evidence of dependent variable variation, for all of the studied independent variable, can be performed by plotting graphs (figure 9).

Fig. 9. Temperature variation graph

4. Conclusions

At the milling of the polymeric composite materials reinforced randomly with fiberglass it is necessary to make the correct choice of the process parameters that are necessary to ensure values of temperature in the cutting area smaller than thermal degradation temperature of the matrix material, during the cutting process.

Application made by using LabView can reveal experimental results with errors and their elimination to determine appropriate mathematical models.

Mathematical modeling of milling process results of the polymeric composite materials reinforced with fiberglass randomly showed that if all parameters cutting regime increase, the temperature developed in the cutting area increases as well. Of cutting regime parameters analyzed, the cutting speed and feed rate have a significant influence on the thermal field of pattern and cutting tool.

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